

Indonesian language teachers' teaching performance and students' learning outcomes

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ABSTRACT

Teachers are an important component in modern society because they have a very extraordinary role in the lives of children, especially in the early years of their development. This study aimed to describe the teaching performance of Indonesian language teachers and how it affects the Indonesian language learning outcomes of state junior high school students of Merauke, Indonesia. To achieve this goal, the researchers used a quantitative approach with a survey research design. Data on the teaching performance of Indonesian language teachers were obtained by distributing a survey questionnaire to students who had been designated as respondents, while data on students' learning outcomes were obtained by getting their academic transcripts. Obtained data were statistically analyzed using the software statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) version 21. The results showed that the teaching performance of Indonesian language teachers has a significant positive effect on the learning outcomes of the state junior high school students of Merauke, Indonesia. The result indicated the importance of the school principals to focus their efforts to improve the teaching performance of Indonesian language teachers in order that students' learning outcomes are adequately addressed.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Education is essentially a conscious effort made by a person or group of people to develop the ability to think and reason logically and responsibly for self-maturation. The development of thinking and reasoning abilities is commonly measured based on certain achievement criteria which are usually indicated by individual and/or group scores. In the context of school education, the value or score of a student's achievement in learning activities is usually described through the value of learning outcomes contained in the academic record [1].

Learning outcomes are defined differently by experts and observers in the field of education. Center for Teaching Innovation of Cornell University [2] defined learning outcomes as the "measurable statements that articulate what students should know, be able to do, or value as a result of completing a learning program." In a similar vein, the Center for Teaching Support and Innovation of University of Toronto [3] defined learning outcomes as the "statements that describe the knowledge and skills students should acquire at the end of a particular course." Likewise, according to the Center for Excellence in Learning and Teaching of University of Galway [4], learning outcomes are "sets of competencies that express what students will know, understand,

or be able to do following the end of a learning process.” Thalib and Sansgiri [5] defined learning outcomes as the degree to which a student, educator, or academic institution has achieved their educational goals, both short-term and long-term. For this study, the learning outcomes referred to the changes in the student’s way of thinking, working, and engaging in social life which is measured based on the Indonesian language academic records of individual students.

Student learning outcomes are one of the most powerful determinants of future earnings [6]–[8], but there is still a persistent learning outcomes gap in Indonesia. Werang and Leba [9] indicated that the eastern part of Indonesia students not performing as well as their counterparts in the western part of Indonesia. These recent reports, of course, were at odds with the accrediting value of the state junior high schools in Papua in general, and Merauke in particular, which are typically rated ‘excellent’. Many factors contribute to these learning outcomes gaps, but those with the largest impact are: i) School factors such as adjustment to curriculum and the availability of teaching-learning facilities [10], teacher preparation and experience [11], and teacher teaching performance [12]; ii) Family factors such as family economic hardship and awareness of education values for the future life of children [10]; iii) Student factors such as student temperament [13], learning motivation [14], learning habits, and preferences [9].

As teacher teaching performance, both within and outside the classroom, is regarded as the most crucial factor influencing student learning outcomes, this study focuses on describing the teaching performance of Indonesian language teachers and how it affects students’ learning outcomes, using the junior high school students of Merauke as the population and samples. Teacher teaching performance is the main indicator in assessing school performance and is largely determined by the level of participation in school organizations [15]. Sonnentag [16] defined teacher teaching performance as a combination of the results of the teacher’s own efforts, abilities, and perceptions about his teaching work both inside and outside the classroom. Rashid and Amin [17] defined teacher teaching performance as the teacher’s ability to combine various relevant inputs to improve the quality of the learning process. So that teachers can participate optimally for the success of students, Werang, Leba, and Pure [10] suggested the importance of providing all the facilities needed by teachers for the smooth running of learning activities in the classroom.

The teaching performance of teachers in schools in general and especially in the classroom is determined by many factors. The first factor is the school principal. The school principals assist teachers with discipline and support teachers in enforcing school rules [18]. Professional school principals do not leave school for no apparent reason and will always accompany teachers and students in the schools they lead. Professional school principals always try to provide positive and constructive input to improve the quality of the learning process and encourage teachers to always use learning facilities and time effectively and efficiently [19]. An effective and efficient school management system by school principals tends to lead to an increase in the quality of education which is very clearly illustrated in student learning outcomes. The increased student learning outcomes are a reflection of the success of the state junior high school principals in empowering teachers in developing various media and learning methods to help the student understand.

Numerous accessible studies [20]–[29] have highlighted how the teaching performance of teachers affected the learning outcomes of students. However, we are enthused to manage additional studies on this topic to address the regional demands of improving the front liners’ capability of mastering the Indonesian language to maintain the national identity in the eastern border area of Indonesia. Besides, the issue of low literacy skills of elementary school graduates in Merauke regency [10] urged us to choose the Indonesian language subject as the focus in describing the learning outcomes among the state junior high schools in Merauke. We do believe, the increased student learning outcomes in Indonesian language subject is a reflection of the success of teachers in guiding the state junior high school students to master literacy skills. As none of the studies have empirically investigated the topic of how Indonesian language teachers’ teaching performance affects students’ learning outcomes in the eastern Indonesia border area as the population and samples, we do believe that the finding of this study may narrow the gap of knowledge in the existing literature. One research question guided the study is “does the teaching performance of teachers affect significantly positively students’ learning outcomes in Indonesian language subjects at the state junior high schools of Merauke?” To answer the research question, a quantitative-survey questionnaire and a documentation study were employed.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Research design

The study described the effect of Indonesian language teachers’ teaching performance on the learning outcomes of the state junior high school students of Merauke, Indonesia. This purpose was attained through the use of a quantitative-survey research design, as it allowed us to gain a greater understanding of the perspective related to teachers’ teaching performance and how it affects student learning outcomes. Since the data of quantitative-survey are typically numerical in nature, the obtained data were treated statistically.

Survey research has four important characteristics [30] as: i) The variables of interest are measured by asking the respondents to express directly their own thoughts, feelings, and behavior; ii) Significant attention is paid to the issue of sampling; iii) It can be carried out in person, by phone, mail, or online; and iv) It can be about polling targets, social attitudes, user preference, or anything else that can be asked about and receive profound answers. We employed a survey research design for the following considerations: i) It is often used to portray human behavior [31]; ii) It allows us to collect information from a group of individuals through their responses to the items of the questionnaire[32]; and iii) It often provided through online such as mail or Google Form [33]. Besides, a survey research design offers many advantages such as easy to get data, inexpensive, and possessing a high degree of statistical significance [34]–[36].

2.2. Participants and data collection

This study was carried out in the state junior high schools of Merauke, Indonesia. The target population of this study is all the state junior high schools in Merauke as they are typically rated excellent in national accreditation and have roughly the same level of learning facilities and outstanding teachers. The study employed two data collection methods. Data related to the teaching performance of teachers were obtained through the distribution of a survey questionnaire containing eight positive items to a total of 309 students, conveniently drawn from among students enrolled in the state junior high schools of Merauke, Indonesia; while data related to the student's learning outcomes in the Indonesian language subject were obtained through the score written in their academic transcripts. To adhere to the Indonesian Government's policy of restricting community activities during the COVID-19 pandemic, the survey questionnaire was distributed to the surveyed students through Google Forms, and students' academic transcripts were obtained with the help of the Indonesian Language Subject teachers.

2.3. Data analysis

The collected data were analyzed using inferential statistics by applying simple linear regression analysis techniques. To obtain an accurate statistical analysis result on the effect of the Indonesian language teachers' teaching performance on the learning outcomes of state junior high school students of Merauke, Indonesia, we employed the statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) version 21. One research hypothesis (known as an alternative hypothesis or H_a) was proposed to be examined, that is 'the teaching performance of Indonesian language teachers has a significant positive effect on the learning outcomes of the state junior high school students of Merauke, Indonesia; whereas null hypothesis (H_0) is that the teaching performance of Indonesian language teachers has a negative effect on the learning outcomes of the state junior high school students of Merauke, Indonesia.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study intended to describe the effect of Indonesian language teachers' teaching performance on the learning outcomes of junior high school students of Merauke, Indonesia. We were really aware that testing the data normality is one of the prerequisites in data analysis using a simple linear regression model. However, due to the vast number of samples in the study, we disregard the prerequisites test [37]. As previously stated, this research data was analyzed statistically using a simple linear regression analysis technique by applying SPSS software version 21. The result of the statistical analysis of the effect of teacher teaching performance on the learning outcomes of junior high school students of Merauke is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The result of data analysis using simple linear regression on the variables studied

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. error of the estimate	R Square change	Change statistics			
						F change	df1	df2	Sig. F change
1	.816 ^a	.665	.664	3.98585	.665	525.012	1	264	.000

(a)=Predictors: (Constant), Teacher_Teaching_Performance

The result of the data analysis presented in Table 1 confirmed the research hypothesis (H_a) and rejected the null hypothesis (H_0) as the coefficient value of R Square (R^2) is .665 and the probability coefficient (Sig. F Change) is .000. It means that adding one point to the teaching performance of the Indonesian language teacher will have an impact on increasing 0.665 points in the learning outcomes of the junior high school students of Merauke, Indonesia. On the other hand, reducing one point from the teaching performance of the Indonesian language teacher will have an impact of decreasing 0.665 points from the learning outcomes of the junior high school students of Merauke, Indonesia.

The teacher is the most crucial element of the educational system in terms of boosting student learning which is critical to their future success. Student success, in turn, should be used as a tool to evaluate teacher teaching performance [38]. The result of data analysis demonstrates that the success of students in school is greatly dependent on the quality of teacher teaching performance because students learn from what teachers teach and do [34]. The higher the teaching performance of the Indonesian language teacher, the higher the learning outcomes of the junior high school students of Merauke, Indonesia; the lower the teaching performance of the Indonesian language teacher, the lower the learning outcomes of the junior high school students of Merauke, Indonesia. The result of this study supports several research findings [23], [24], [29], [39] that the teaching performance of teachers has a significant positive effect on student learning outcomes.

Teachers can positively impact student learning by encouraging their students. Teachers' support can be crucial to students' learning and affective outcomes as students spend a significant amount of time with their teachers at school. Numerous empirical types of research [40]–[42] have demonstrated a substantial beneficial correlation between teacher support and favorable academic emotions. Expectations and contingencies are structured. Involvement involves “affection, resource dedication, student comprehension, or reliability” [43].

Teacher support involves sovereignty, construct, and attachment. Support for autonomy is the teacher's provision of choice, relevance, or respect to students. Longobardi *et al.* [44] claimed that teachers who support students demonstrate concern and respect for their students and these students, in turn, respond to this concern and respect for their teacher by sticking to classroom rules. Teachers who yell at and criticize their students, on the other hand, often see a decrease in their students' care for their teachers and a decrease in their cooperative classroom actions [45].

Students learning outcomes and accomplishments are influenced by the teacher's thoughts and expectations of his or her students. The teacher's influence, ideas, and expectations of students' abilities impact their academic performance. Students begin to believe in themselves when teachers believe in them. Students internalize their teachers' beliefs about them and accept them as a part of who they are and what they can do. Increased students' academic performance is a reflection of the success of teachers in teaching. From this perspective, students' inability to master reading, writing, and arithmetic in Southern Papua, as demonstrated by Werang, Leba, and Pure [10], should be viewed as evidence of teachers' ineffectiveness in facilitating students' improvement.

According to Diaz and Requejo [46], effective teachers are those who make an effective preparation for the student's activity and lesson delivery as well as homework to strengthen students' active learning. Research on teacher teaching performance in the classroom exhibited that effective teachers are those who are able to employ a variety of teaching strategies and exhibit a flexible style rather than a single, inflexible approach. Effective teachers should use various techniques to help students improve their academic performance and are capable of adapting their teaching style to the requirements and preferences of diverse learners [47].

Effective teachers are considered agents of change, promoting changes in students' knowledge, abilities, and attitudes [48]. In this viewpoint, teachers' adaptability to the student's preferred mode of learning may be the most important factor in bringing about the shift in the educational landscape [49]. Teachers' accountability for students' learning outcomes might cause it challenging for them to engage with students in a meaningful way that helps them accomplish targets and achieve their goals. Deppeler, Loreman, and Smith [50] claimed that teachers would be able to change their teaching practices if they take time to reflect on them and engage themselves in process of reviewing their own conceptions of teaching practices.

4. CONCLUSION

Quality education is critical to supplying the workforce needed to create prosperity and raise living standards. This study elucidates the effect of the teaching performance of Indonesian language teachers on student learning outcomes. The conclusion depicted from the data analysis result is that the teaching performance of the Indonesian language teacher has a significant positive effect on the learning outcomes of junior high school students of Merauke, Indonesia, as indicated by the R^2 value of .665 and the probability value (Sig. F Change) of .000. It implies that 66.5% of the learning outcomes of junior high school students of Merauke, Indonesia, is explained by the teaching performance of the Indonesian language teacher; while the remainder is explained by other variables. Based on this finding, the following recommendations can be made: i) The findings of this study can serve as input for the school principals to focus their efforts on improving teachers' teaching performance, which results in the improvement of students' learning outcomes; and ii) The findings of this study can also serve as input for Indonesian language teachers at the junior high schools of Merauke, Indonesia, to work optimally for the success of the students they teach.

Student learning outcomes is a dynamic marvel as it is influenced by a wide variety of factors, such as school principal leadership, teacher teaching commitment, teacher teaching performance, and teacher working conditions. Given that this study concentrated on a single factor, teacher teaching performance, future studies examining a broader range of variables is strongly recommended. In addition, this study was only conducted in the state junior high schools of Southern Papua and, therefore, the findings of this study should be strictly interpreted. In order to generalize the findings, further studies be conducted across a larger range of area.

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